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Investigating the Relationship between University Students' Cyberloafing Profiles and Life Goals according to Various Variables

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Abstract

Cyberloafing is a widely recognized concept associated with the Internet, which has a wide usage area today. Cyberloafing is extensively noticed, particularly among young people, and its association with a variety of variables is being researched. In this study, university students' life goals and cyberloafing profiles were analyzed on the basis of gender, age, class, grade point average, relationship status, faculty, foreign language knowledge, daily digital tool usage time, age of first using the internet, and digital devices used. The research's study group was comprised of university students from İzmir's public and private universities. 334 students posted data. The study excluded 31 participants who were found to have missing or incomplete data. The study group included 303 students. As data collection instruments, the cyberloafing scale, life goals scale, and personal information form were employed. According to the data, there is a positive and moderate association between students' levels of cyberloafing and their life goals. Cyberloafing varies according to criteria such as age, gender, faculty, and daily internet usage. Similarly, it was found that life goals changed depending on department, relationship status, and daily internet usage time.

Keywords: Cyberloafing, Life Goals, University Students

1. Introduction

1.1 Definition of the Problem

Internet use is becoming more and more widespread in today's world and the average duration of daily internet use has been reported to be 6 hours and 55 minutes (We are social, 2021). Calculated for the age range of 16-64, this duration amounts to nearly 25 % of a day. Thus, it is clear that internet use takes up a considerable amount of time in an individual's life and inevitably influences his/her short-term and long-term goals. The percentage of internet users in Türkiye is 92 (Turkish Statistical Institute, 2021). While internet use is generally associated with useful practices such as education, shopping and online transactions etc, it sometimes leads to certain problematic behaviors including online game addiction and cybercrimes etc. One of the problematic internet uses recently

added to the list is cyberloafing. Accessing education and teaching environments via the internet, free wi-fi services provided by all universities and proliferation of smart mobile phones among university students (Gökçearslan et al., 2018) are some of the determining criteria for the presence of cyberloafing.

Cyberloafing is defined as students' engaging in some activities rather than those related to the lesson during a lesson such as surfing on the internet and watching videos etc. (Kalaycı, 2010; Lim & Chen, 2012). Ugrin et.al (2008) defined cyberloafing as all the activities causing individuals to spend their time inefficiently on the internet. The literature on cyberloafing introduces various classifications proposed by the researchers focusing on the issue (Blau et.al., 2006; İnce & Gül, 2011; Mahatanankoon et.al., 2004). One of the most acknowledged classifications was suggested by Blanchard and Henle (2008) under two categories. The first one called "serious cyberloafing behaviors" involve spending active time on gambling/betting websites, watching or downloading illegal online content, downloading music from illegal resources and spending time on adult websites etc. "Minor cyberloafing behaviors", on the other hand, include certain behaviors and activities such as sending and receiving personal e-mails, visiting sports or news websites, spending time visiting websites related to one's personal interests. Thus, it is clear that cyberloafing is a significant factor in one's engaging in certain activities to achieve his/her short-term and long-term goals.

Life Goals are discussed and examined under different categories within the framework of factors related to how one makes sense of life. According to Heady (2008), success involves being active in family and social life and helping others. Having life goals and regulating life accordingly are considered one of the most important sources of happiness (Lyubomirsky et.al., 2005). Kasser and Ryan (2001) discuss individuals' life goals under two dimensions: internal life and external life. Within the framework of social learning theory, Rotter highlights that life goals are one of three determining factors that affect human behaviors.

Life goals of university students were examined in relation to various variables. To illustrate, Ciğerci et.al (2020) investigated the relationship between life goals and smart phone addiction in a study conducted with 677 university students who study health sciences. Similarly, some researchers explored the relationship between life goals and self-efficacy satisfaction (Aydıner, 2011), its effects on subjective well-being and psychological need satisfaction İlhan and Özbay (2010) and meaning of life (Çelik (2016). Short-term and long-term goals of university students often depend on various factors. Behaviors they display while using the internet play a determining role in achieving their future life goals since these behaviors take up an important part of their daily life.

1.2 Purpose of the Study

The study aims to examine the relationship between university students' life goals and cyberloafing profiles according to different variables. To achieve this purpose, university students' life goals and cyberloafing profiles were examined in terms of gender, age, class year, GPA (grand point average), relationship status, the faculty attended, knowledge of foreign language, duration of digital devices use a day, the age when they started to use the internet and digital devices used. The primary research question of the study is "Is there a significant relationship between university students' life goals and cyberloafing profiles?"

Secondary research questions of the study are as follows:

Do university students' cyberloafing profiles differ according to various variables (gender, age, class year, GPA, relationship status, the faculty attended, knowledge of foreign language, duration of digital devices use a day, the age when they started to use the internet and digital devices used)?

Do university students' life goals differ according to various variables (gender, age, class year, GPA, relationship status, the faculty attended, knowledge of foreign language, duration of digital devices use a day, the age when they started to use the internet and digital devices used)?

2. Method

The survey model, which is one of the quantitative research approaches, was used to conduct the study. The cross-sectional survey approach will be employed since the study data will be collected all at once.

2.1 Participants

The research's study group includes of university students from Izmir's public and private universities. A total of 334 students provided data. The study excluded 31 participants who were found to have missing or incomplete data. The study group had 303 students. Table 1 shows the demographic characteristics of the participants, such as gender, grade level, age distribution, grade distributions, relationship status, and the faculties they studied.

Table 1: Demographic characteristics of the participants

Gender	n	%
Woman	203	67.0
Man	100	33.0
Grade Level		
1 st Grade	48	15.8
2 nd Grade	65	21.5
3 rd Grade	20	6.6
4 th Grade	170	56.1
Age Distribution		
17-21	132	43.6
22-26	171	56.4
Grade Distribution		
1.00 – 1.99	14	4.6
2.00 – 2.99	94	31.0
3.00 – 4.00	90	29.7
Relationship Status		
Single	135	44.6
Married	39	12.9
Have an ongoing relationship	77	25.4
Not have an ongoing relationship	52	17.2
Faculty		
Education	106	35.0
Science – Literature	53	17.5
Economics – Business	17	5.6
Nursing	48	15.8
Engineering	4	1.3
Fine Arts	25	8.3
Architecture	1	0.3
Theology	31	10.2
Conservatory	18	5.9

The English, German and French foreign language levels of the participants were determined to be graded at beginner, intermediate and advanced levels. The characteristics of the participants' foreign language level information are given in Table 2.

Table 2: Foreign language levels of the participants

English Level	n	%
Beginner	114	37.6
Intermediate	114	37.6
Advanced	44	14.5

No Knowledge	31	10.2
German Level		
Beginner	43	14.2
Intermediate	12	4.0
Advanced	12	4.0
No Knowledge	236	77.9
French Level		
Beginner	9	3.0
Intermediate	2	0.7
Advanced	-	-
No Knowledge	292	96.4

The characteristics of the participants' daily digital tool usage time, time of starting to use the internet and the level of the most used device while connecting to the internet are given in Table 3.

Table 3: Digital technology usage status of the participants

Daily Digital Tool Usage Time	n	%
Less than 2 hours	71	23.4
More than 2 hours – less than 4 hours	134	44.2
More than 4 hours	98	32.3
Time to Start Using the Internet		
Primary school and before	75	24.8
Middle school	124	40.9
High school and after	104	34.3
Most Used Device While Connecting to the Internet		
Desktop computer	69	22.8
Notebook	167	55.1
Tablet computer	58	19.1
Smart phone	271	89.4
Smart watch	5	1.7

2.2 Data Collection Tools

In the study, Akbulut et al. (2016) “Cyber Loafing Scale” and Aydiner (2011) “Life Goals Scale” and personal information form prepared by researchers were used.

2.3 Cyberloafing Scale

The total variance of the scale was determined as 70.44%. Scale items are grouped under five factors. The factors were determined as sharing, shopping, updating in real time, accessing online content and playing games. Kaiser-Meyer Oklin (KMO) sample adequacy measurement value was calculated as 0.921. The internal consistency coefficient for the overall scale was found to be 0.942. It is a 5 likert type scale with 30 questions.

2.3.1 Life Goals Scale

The total variance of the scale was determined as 56.87%. The scale items developed in a five-point Likert type are grouped under five factors. Factors were determined as personal development, financial gain, physical appearance, social responsibility and individual awareness. Kaiser-Meyer-Oklin (KMO) sample adequacy measurement value was calculated as 0.900. It is a 5 likert type scale with 30 questions.

2.3.2 Personal Information Form

It was organized by the researchers to determine the characteristics of the participants in line with the purpose of the research.

3. Findings

The data obtained within the scope of the research were analyzed and answers were sought to the research problems. The findings obtained in this context are presented below.

3.1 Investigation of the Relationship Between University Students' Cyberloafing Levels and Life Goals

Table 4 shows that there is a positive and moderate relationship between cyberloafing levels and life goals ($r = 0.428$, $p < .001$). The relationship between cyberloafing levels and sub-dimensions of the life goals scale was also examined. According to this review, it is seen that there is a positive and moderate relationship between cyberloafing levels and physical appearance ($r = 0.497$, $p < .001$) and financial gain ($r = 0.493$, $p < .001$) sub-dimensions. Since the relationships between cyberloafing levels and the social responsibility, individual awareness and personal development sub-dimensions of the life goals scale are $p > 0.05$, the relationship between them is not significant.

Table 4: Correlation analysis of the relationship between cyberloafing levels and life goals

n = 303	Cyberloafing	Life goals
Cyberloafing	-	0.428**
Life goals	0.428**	-

** Significant at the .001 level.

3.2 Investigation of University Students' Cyberloafing Levels According to Various Variables

Cyberloafing levels of university students were investigated according to gender, age, class, grade point average, relationship status, faculty, foreign language knowledge, daily digital tool usage time, age of starting to use the internet and digital devices used. The findings are presented below.

3.2.1 Investigation of University Students' Cyberloafing Levels by Gender

In order to determine whether the cyberloafing levels of the participants changed according to gender, an independent sample t-test analysis was performed (Table 5). The results of the analysis show that cyberloafing levels make a significant difference according to gender ($t(301) = -3.701$, $p < .001$). Cyberloafing levels of male students ($\bar{X} = 94.20$) are statistically significantly higher than female students' ($\bar{X} = 85.78$) cyberloafing levels.

Table 5: Independent Sample t-Test Analysis Results on Cyberloafing Levels by Gender

	n	$\bar{X}$	SD	Df	t	p
Woman	203	85.78	18.67	301	-3.701	.001
Man	100	94.20	18.54			

3.2.2 Investigation of University Students' Cyberloafing Levels by Age

The age distribution of the participants was categorized in two groups as 17-21 and 22-26. Independent sample t-test analysis was performed to determine whether the levels of cyberloafing changed according to age groups (Table 6). The results of the analysis show that cyberloafing levels make a significant difference according to age ($t(301) = 3.451$, $p < .001$). The cyberloafing levels of the students in the 17-21 age category ($\bar{X} = 92.77$) are statistically significantly higher than the cyberloafing levels of the students in the 22-26 age category ($\bar{X} = 85.30$).

Table 6: Independent Sample t-Test Analysis Results on Cyberloafing Levels by Age

	n	$\bar{X}$	SD	Df	t	p
17-21	132	92.77	17.94	301	3.451	.001
22-26	171	85.30	19.23			

3.2.3 Investigation of University Students' Cyberloafing Levels by Grade Level

One-way analysis of variance (ANOVA) was performed to determine whether the cyberloafing levels of the participants changed according to the grade level (Table 7). Analysis results mean that there is a significant difference between cyberloafing levels in terms of class level ($F(3, 299) = 3.238, p < .05$). The effect size of this difference in the level of cyberloafing between the groups is small (eta-squared = .031). According to the results of Scheffe test performed to examine the differences between grade levels, the difference between 2nd grade students ($\bar{X} = 94.62$) and 4th grade students ($\bar{X} = 88.56$) is statistically significant ($p < .05$).

Table 7: One-Way Analysis of Variance Results on Cyberloafing Levels by Class Level

	n	$\bar{X}$	SD	F (3, 299)	p
1 st Grade	48	87.90	20.90	3.238	.05
2 nd Grade	65	94.62	18.04		
3 rd Grade	20	90.55	19.87		
4 th Grade	170	88.56	18.35		

3.2.4 Investigation of University Students' Cyberloafing Levels by Grade Point Average

The grade point averages of the participants were categorized in three groups as 1.00 – 1.99, 2.00 – 2.99 and 3.00 – 4.00. ANOVA was conducted to determine whether the cyberloafing levels of the participants changed according to their grade point average (Table 8). Analysis results mean that there is no significant difference between cyberloafing levels in terms of grade point average ($F(2, 195) = .441, p > .05$).

Table 8: One-Way Analysis of Variance Results on Cyberloafing Levels by Grade Point Average

	n	$\bar{X}$	SD	F (2, 195)	p
1.00 – 1.99	14	90.07	18.30	.441	.64
2.00 – 2.99	94	92.46	18.88		
3.00 – 4.00	90	89.94	18.52		

3.2.5 Investigation of University Students' Cyberloafing Levels by Relationship Status

ANOVA was conducted to determine whether the cyberloafing levels of the participants changed according to their relationship status (Table 9). The results of the analysis mean that there is a significant difference between the levels of cyberloafing in terms of relationship status ($F(3, 299) = 19.013, p < .001$). The effect size of this difference in the level of cyberloafing between the groups is high (eta-square = .16). According to the results of the Scheffe test, which was conducted to examine the differences between the relationship status, the difference between single students ($\bar{X} = 88.44$), students who are in an ongoing relationship ($\bar{X} = 93.05$) and students who do not have an ongoing relationship ($\bar{X} = 95.61$) and married students ($\bar{X} = 70.23$). the differences are statistically significant ($p < .001$).

Table 9: One-Way Analysis of Variance Results on Cyberloafing Levels by Relationship Status

	n	$\bar{X}$	SD	F (3, 299)	p
Single	135	88.44	18.32	19.013	.001
Married	39	70.23	15.76		
Have an ongoing relationship	77	93.05	16.78		
Not have an ongoing relationship	52	95.94	17.64		

3.2.6 Investigation of University Students' Cyberloafing Levels by Faculty

ANOVA was conducted to determine whether the cyberloafing levels of the participants changed according to the faculties of education (Table 10). The results of the analysis mean that there is a significant difference between the levels of cyberloafing in terms of relationship status ($F(7, 294) = 9.875, p < .001$). The effect size of this difference in the level of cyberloafing between the groups is high ($\eta^2 = .19$). According to the results of the Scheffe test performed to examine the differences between the faculties of education, the differences between the students of the Faculty of Theology ($\bar{X} = 65.42$) and the other faculties are statistically significant ($p < .001$).

Table 10: One-Way Analysis of Variance Results of Cyberloafing Levels by Faculty

	n	$\bar{X}$	SD	F (7, 294)	p
Education	106	91.73	18.22	9.875	.001
Science – Literature	53	86.74	15.72		
Economics – Business	17	90.29	18.61		
Nursing	48	95.67	19.18		
Engineering	4	93.00	20.49		
Fine Arts	25	91.84	18.48		
Theology	31	65.42	11.33		
Conservatory	18	90.11	15.74		

3.2.7 Investigation of University Students' Cyberloafing Levels According to Foreign Language Knowledge

Data on whether the participants knew English, German and French were obtained. An independent sample t-test analysis was conducted to determine whether the cyberloafing levels of the participants changed according to whether they knew English or not (Table 11). The results of the analysis show that the levels of cyberloafing make a significant difference according to whether the participants know English or not ($t(300) = 3.330, p < .001$). The cyberloafing levels of the students who speak English ($\bar{X} = 89.86$) are statistically significantly higher than the cyberloafing levels of the students who do not speak English ($\bar{X} = 78.22$).

Table 11: Independent Sample t-Test Analysis Results on Cyberloafing Levels by English Knowledge

	n	$\bar{X}$	SD	Df	t	p
English Speaking	270	89.86	18.24	300	3.330	.001
No English Knowledge	32	78.22	22.26			

An independent sample t-test analysis was conducted to determine whether the cyberloafing levels of the participants changed according to whether they knew German or not (Table 12). The results of the analysis show that the levels of cyberloafing do not make a significant difference according to whether the participants know German or not ($t(300) = 1.187, p > .05$).

Table 12: Independent Sample t-Test Analysis Results Regarding the Levels of Cyberloafing by Knowledge of German

	n	$\bar{X}$	SD	Df	t	p
German Speaking	66	90.83	16.29	300	1.187	.287
No German Knowledge	236	88.01	19.69			

The Mann-Whitney U test was conducted to determine whether the cyberloafing levels of the participants changed according to whether they knew French or not (Table 13). The results of the analysis show that the levels of cyberloafing do not make a significant difference according to whether the participants know French or not ($Z = -1.071, p > .05$).

Table 13: Independent Sample t-Test Analysis Results on the Levels of Cyberloafing by Knowledge of French

	n	Rank Average	Rank Sum	U	p
French Speaking	11	179.18	1971.00	-1.071	.284

No French Knowledge	291	150.45	43782.00
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3.2.8 Investigation of University Students' Cyberloafing Levels by Daily Digital Tool Usage Time

The daily digital tool usage time of the participants was categorized into three groups as less than 2 hours, more than 2 hours – less than 4 hours and more than 4 hours. ANOVA was conducted to determine whether the cyberloafing levels of the participants changed according to the daily digital tool usage time (Table 14). The results of the analysis mean that there is a significant difference between the levels of cyberloafing in terms of relationship status ($F(2, 300) = 16.118, p < .001$). The effect size of this difference in the level of cyberloafing between the groups is high (eta-square = .097). According to the results of the Scheffe test, which was conducted to examine the differences between daily digital tool usage time, students with more than 4 hours of daily digital tool use ($\bar{X} = 94.92$) and students with more than 2 hours – less than 4 hours ($\bar{X} = 89.01$) compared to those with less than 2 hours. the differences between students ($\bar{X} = 78.92$) were statistically significant ($p < .001$).

Table 14: One-Way Analysis of Variance Results on Cyberloafing Levels by Daily Digital Tool Usage Time

	n	$\bar{X}$	SD	F (2, 300)	p
Less than 2 hours	71	78.92	21.17	16.118	.001
More than 2 hours – less than 4 hours	134	89.01	17.33		
More than 4 hours	98	94.92	16.77		

3.2.9 Investigation of University Students' Cyberloafing Levels by the Time of Starting to Use the Internet

The time when the participants started using the internet was categorized in three groups as Primary School and before, Middle School, High School and later. ANOVA was conducted to determine whether the cyberloafing levels of the participants changed according to the time they started using the internet (Table 15). The results of the analysis mean that there is a significant difference between the levels of cyberloafing in terms of relationship status ($F(2, 300) = 20.955, p < .001$). The effect size of this difference in the level of cyberloafing between the groups is high (eta-square = .123). According to the results of the Scheffe test, which was conducted to examine the differences between the times of starting to use the internet, the difference between the students who started to use the internet at and before primary school ($\bar{X} = 94.84$) and the students who were in middle school ($\bar{X} = 92.39$) compared to the students who were at high school and later ($\bar{X} = 79.46$). the differences are statistically significant ($p < .001$).

Table 15: One-Way Analysis of Variance Results of Cyberloafing Levels by Time of Starting to Use the Internet

	n	$\bar{X}$	SD	F (2, 300)	p
Primary school and before	75	94.84	16.65	20.955	.001
Middle school	124	92.39	16.68		
High school and after	104	79.46	19.97		

3.2.10 Investigation of the Cyberloafing Levels of University Students According to the Most Used Digital Devices

An independent sample t-test analysis was conducted to determine whether the cyberloafing levels of the participants changed according to the most used digital devices. It is seen that cyberloafing levels do not make a significant difference according to whether the most used device type is desktop computer or not ($t(301) = -.500, p > .05$). It is seen that cyberloafing levels make a significant difference according to whether the most used device type is laptop or not ($t(301) = 2.977, p < .05$). The cyberloafing levels of the students whose most used device type is laptop computer ($\bar{X} = 91.46$) are statistically significantly higher than the cyberloafing levels of the students who do not ($\bar{X} = 85.00$). It is seen that cyberloafing levels make a significant difference according to whether the most used device type is tablet computer or not ($t(301) = 2.286, p < .05$). The cyberloafing levels of students whose most used device type is tablet computer ($\bar{X} = 93.66$) are statistically significantly higher than the cyberloafing

levels of students who do not ($\bar{X}$ = 87.35). It is seen that the levels of cyberloafing do not make a significant difference according to whether the most used device type is a smartphone ($t(301) = -.375, p > .05$).

3.3 Investigation of University Students' Life Goals According to Various Variables

Life goals of university students were examined according to gender, age, class, grade point average, relationship status, faculty of education, foreign language knowledge, daily digital tool usage time, age of starting to use the internet and digital devices used. The findings are presented below.

3.3.1 Investigation of University Students' Life Goals by Gender

An independent sample t-test analysis was performed to determine whether the life goals of the participants changed according to gender (Table 16). The results of the analysis show that life goals do not make a significant difference according to gender ($t(301) = -.190, p > .05$). There was no significant difference between male students' life goals ($\bar{X}$ = 114.71) and female students' ($\bar{X}$ = 114.36) life goals.

Table 16: Results of Independent Sample t-Test Analysis of Life Goals by Gender

	n	$\bar{X}$	SD	Df	t	p
Woman	203	114.36	13.13	301	-.190	.840
Man	100	114.71	15.68			

3.3.2 Investigation of University Students' Life Goals by Age

An independent sample t-test analysis was performed to determine whether the life goals of the participants changed according to age (Table 17). The results of the analysis show that life goals do not make a significant difference according to age ($t(301) = 1.885, p > .05$).

Table 17: Results of Independent Sample t-Test Analysis of Life Goals by Age

	n	$\bar{X}$	SD	Df	t	p
17-21	132	116.20	13.85	301	1.885	.060
22-26	171	113.15	14.01			

3.3.3 Investigation of University Students' Life Goals by Grade Level

ANOVA was conducted to determine whether the life goals of the participants changed according to the grade level (Table 18). Analysis results mean that there is no significant difference between life goals in terms of class level ($F(3, 299) = .508, p > .05$).

Table 18: One-Way Analysis of Variance Results Related to Class Level of Life Goals

	n	$\bar{X}$	SD	F (3, 299)	p
1 st Grade	48	115.3542	13.28171	.508	.677
2 nd Grade	65	114.8462	14.70250		
3 rd Grade	20	117.3500	12.21421		
4 th Grade	170	113.7529	14.17215		

3.3.4 Investigation of University Students' Life Goals by Grade Point Average

ANOVA was conducted to determine whether the life goals of the participants changed according to their grade point average (Table 19). Analysis results mean that there is no significant difference between life goals in terms of grade point average ($F(2, 195) = .551, p > .05$).

Table 19: One-Way Analysis of Variance Results on Grade Point Average of Life Goals

	n	$\bar{X}$	SD	F (2, 195)	p
1.00 – 1.99	48	116.86	16.78	.551	.577
2.00 – 2.99	65	114.38	14.64		
3.00 – 4.00	20	116.54	14.62		

3.3.5 Investigation of University Students' Life Goals by Relationship Status

ANOVA was conducted to determine whether the life goals of the participants changed according to their relationship status (Table 20). Analysis results mean that there is a significant difference between life goals in terms of relationship status ($F(3, 299) = 6.159, p < .001$). The effect size of this difference on life goals between groups was low (eta-square = .033). According to the results of the Scheffe test conducted to examine the differences between the relationship status; The differences between students ($\bar{X} = 119.46$) who do not have a lasting relationship compared to married students ($\bar{X} = 108.10$) are statistically significant ($p < .005$). The differences between students in a continuing relationship ($\bar{X} = 116.60$) compared to married students ($\bar{X} = 108.10$) were statistically significant ($p < .05$).

Table 20: One-Way Analysis of Variance Results on the Relationship of Life Goals

	n	$\bar{X}$	SD	F (3, 299)	p
Single	135	113.19	14.32	6.159	.001
Married	39	108.10	11.81		
Have an ongoing relationship	77	116.60	13.34		
Not have an ongoing relationship	52	119.46	13.63		

3.3.6 Investigation of University Students' Life Goals by Faculty

ANOVA was conducted to determine whether the life goals of the participants changed according to the faculties of education (Table 21). Analysis results mean that there is a significant difference in terms of life goals relationship status ($F(7, 294) = 4.083, p < .001$). The effect size of this difference on life goals between the groups was high (eta-square = .089). According to the results of the Scheffe test conducted to examine the differences between the faculties of education, the differences between the students of the Faculty of Theology ($\bar{X} = 106.19$), the students of the Faculty of Education ($\bar{X} = 116.95$) and the Faculty of Nursing ($\bar{X} = 118.54$) are statistically significant ($p < .005$).

Table 21: One-Way Analysis of Variance Results of Life Goals and Faculty

	n	$\bar{X}$	SD	F (7, 294)	p
Education	106	116.95	12.12	4.083	.001
Science – Literature	53	110.04	13.83		
Economics – Business	17	112.00	14.34		
Nursing	48	118.54	14.59		
Engineering	4	116.00	16.83		
Fine Arts	25	117.96	16.28		
Theology	31	106.19	11.03		
Conservatory	18	116.06	12.44		

3.3.7 Investigation of University Students' Life Goals According to Foreign Language Knowledge

An independent sample t-test analysis was performed to determine whether the life goals of the participants changed depending on whether they knew English or not (Table 22). The results of the analysis show that life goals make a significant difference according to whether the participants know English or not ($t(300) = 2.253, p < .05$). The life goals of students who speak English ($\bar{X} = 115.24$) are statistically significantly higher than the levels of life goals of students who do not speak English ($\bar{X} = 109.47$).

Table 22: Independent Sample t-Test Analysis Results Regarding Life Goals According to English Knowledge

	n	$\bar{X}$	SD	Df	t	p
English Speaking	270	115.24	13.55	300	2.253	.05
No English Knowledge	32	109.47	14.93			

An independent sample t-test analysis was conducted to determine whether the life goals of the participants changed according to their knowledge of German or not (Table 23). The results of the analysis show that life goals do not make a significant difference according to whether the participants know German or not ($t(300) = -.034, p > .05$).

Table 23: Independent Sample t-Test Analysis Results Regarding Life Goals According to Knowledge of German

	n	$\bar{X}$	SD	Df	t	p
German Speaking	66	114.58	13.46	300	-.034	.973
No German Knowledge	236	114.64	13.91			

The Mann-Whitney U test was conducted to determine whether the life goals of the participants changed depending on whether they knew French or not (Table 24). The results of the analysis show that life goals do not make a significant difference according to whether the participants speak French or not ($Z = -.839, p > .05$).

Table 24: Independent Sample t-Test Analysis Results Regarding Life Goals by Knowledge of French

	n	Rank Average	Rank Sum	U	p
French Speaking	11	129.82	1428.00	-.839	.401
No French Knowledge	261	152.32	44325.00		

3.3.8 Investigation of University Students' Life Goals According to Daily Digital Tool Usage Time

ANOVA was conducted to determine whether the life goals of the participants changed according to the daily digital tool usage time (Table 25). The analysis results mean that there is a significant difference between life goals in terms of relationship status ($F(2, 300) = 9.273, p < .001$). The effect size of this difference on life goals between groups was low (eta-square = .058). According to the results of the Scheffe test, which was conducted to examine the differences between daily digital tool usage time, students with more than 4 hours of daily digital tool use ($\bar{X} = 117.80$) and students with more than 2 hours – less than 4 hours ($\bar{X} = 115.32$) compared to those with less than 2 hours, the differences between students ($\bar{X} = 108.94$) were statistically significant ($p < .001$).

Table 25: One-Way Analysis of Variance Results for Life Goals by Daily Digital Tool Usage Duration

	n	$\bar{X}$	SD	F (2, 300)	p
Less than 2 hours	71	108.94	16.72	9.273	.001
More than 2 hours – less than 4 hours	134	115.32	12.15		
More than 4 hours	98	117.80	12.36		

3.3.9 Investigation of University Students' Life Goals by the Time of Starting to Use the Internet

ANOVA was conducted to determine whether the life goals of the participants changed according to the time they started using the Internet (Table 26). The analysis results mean that there is a significant difference between life goals in terms of relationship status ($F(2, 300) = 4.541, p < .05$). The effect size of this difference on life goals between groups was low (eta-square = .029). According to the results of the Scheffe test, which was conducted to examine the differences between the time to start using the internet, the differences between the students whose starting time to use the internet were in middle school ($\bar{X} = 116.56$) and those who were in high school and later ($\bar{X} = 111.36$) were statistically significant ($p < .05$).

Table 26: One-Way Analysis of Variance Results of Life Goals by Time of Starting to Use the Internet

	n	$\bar{X}$	SD	F (2, 300)	p
Primary school and before	75	115.92	13.08368	4.541	.011
Middle school	124	116.56	13.29607		
High school and after	104	111.36	14.38944		

3.3.10 Investigation of University Students' Life Goals According to the Most Used Digital Devices

An independent sample t-test analysis was conducted to determine whether the life goal of the participants changed according to the most used digital devices. It is seen that there is no significant difference according to whether the most used device type is desktop computer or not ($t(301) = -.121, p > .05$). It is seen that there is no significant difference according to whether the most used device type is laptop computer or not ($t(301) = 1.138, p > .05$). It is seen that there is a significant difference according to whether the most used device type is tablet computer or not ($t(301) = 2.443, p < .05$). The life goals of the students whose most used device type is tablet computer ($\bar{X} = 118.57$) are statistically significantly higher than the life goals of the students who do not ($\bar{X} = 113.69$). It is seen that life goals do not make a significant difference according to whether the most used device is a smartphone ($t(301) = -.094, p > .05$).

4. Discussion

In the present study, university students' life goals and cyberloafing profiles were examined in terms of gender, age, class year, GPA, relationship status, the faculty attended, knowledge of foreign language, duration of digital devices use a day, the age when they started to use the internet and digital devices used. According to the results, there is a positive and medium level correlation between students' life goals and cyberloafing levels. The study also investigated the correlation between cyberloafing levels and dimensions of Life Goals Scale. Accordingly, the results showed a positive and medium level correlation between cyberloafing levels and "physical appearance" and "financial income" dimensions while no correlation was found for "social responsibility", "personal awareness" and "personal development" dimensions. Some studies in the literature examining the variables related to cyberloafing also found medium level of cyberloafing in university students. Moreover, there are studies reporting that cyberloafing can correlate with various personal and environmental variables (Gezgin & Sarsar, 2020; Şenel et.al., 2019).

The study found a significant difference in participants' cyberloafing levels in terms of gender. Cyberloafing levels of male students were significantly higher than those of female students. Some studies dealing with this issue also report similar findings (Akbulut et.al., 2017; Dursun et.al., 2018; Lenhart, 2015; Lim & Chen, 2012; Şenel, 2019). The findings also revealed a significant difference in cyberloafing levels for age variable. Cyberloafing levels of the students at 17-21 age range were significantly higher than the levels of those at 22-26 age range. The study by Ekinci (2022) reported the presence of a significant difference between 18-19 and 22-23 age range in terms of social media use and Chou et al (2009) also found that social media use is more popular among young people. In parallel with this finding, the study showed a significant difference in cyberloafing levels in terms of class year. The difference between 2nd year students and 4th year students was also statistically significant. Young people are known to spend more time on the internet (We are social, 2022). As the results of the present study indicate, the increase in internet use correlates with cyberloafing.

How much time the participants spend using the digital devices in a day was grouped under three categories: less than two hours; more than 2 hours – less than 4 hours; and more than 4 hours. The study found a significant difference between the duration of time spent daily on digital devices and cyberloafing levels. The differences between the participants who use digital devices more than 4 hours a day - more than 2 hours and less than 4 hours a day were statistically significant than the participants who spend less than 2 hours a day on digital devices. Some studies in the literature also reported a correlation between duration of internet use and cyberloafing (Baturay & Toker, 2015; Gülnar, 2020; Karaoğlan-Yılmaz et.al., 2015; Lenhart, 2015; Lim & Chen, 2012; Şenel, 2019). However, not a significant difference was found between cyberloafing levels and GPA (grand point average). Although cyberloafing is generally considered a negative behavior, there are some studies emphasizing its positive

effects as well. Tan and Demir (2018) suggested that cyberloafing might be useful for both personal and institutional development when it assumes a facilitating role in learning. In addition, how much time students spend using digital devices significantly differs according to their life goals.

The results of the current study showed a significant difference in cyberloafing levels according to the participants' relationship status. The differences between married students and single students as well as those with an ongoing relationship and those who do not have any ongoing relationships were significant. Similarly, there was a significant correlation between life goals and relationship status. One of the categories for one's life goals is the presence of a relationship (Emmons, 1999; Wong, 1998). Therefore, relationship status of the participants is expected to differ according to life goals.

One of the results of the present study is the significant difference between the faculties attended according to both cyberloafing levels and life goals. Faculties preferred by students are somewhat related to their life goals (Şahin et.al 2011). Individuals' setting their life goals and doing their best to achieve them are clearly effective and significant factors (Myers and Deiner, 1995). Therefore, faculty preferences of university students can be considered a determining factor accordingly.

The present study performed analyses to determine whether cyberloafing levels of the participants differ according to their knowledge of English, German and French. The results showed a significant difference in their cyberloafing levels in terms of knowledge of English, while no significant differences were found for knowledge of German and French. The participant students who know English had significantly higher cyberloafing levels than those who do not know this language. English is the most widespread language used on the internet. According to the research by W3Techs, the content of more than 56% of the websites published on the internet is in English (Internet world stats, 2022). As students have better command of English, the number of platforms they can access via the internet also increases. Thus, knowledge of English can correlate with cyberloafing behavior. Similarly, life goals of students who know English were found to be significantly higher than those of the students who do not know English. According to Heady (2008), being successful is one of the basic life goals and knowledge of English can be evaluated in relation with this life goal.

The time when the participants started to use the internet were grouped under three categories: primary school and before; middle school; and high school and later. The study found a significant difference in participants' cyberloafing levels in terms of the time when they started to use the internet. The students who started to use the internet in high school and later significantly differed from those who started to use the internet primary school and before and middle school. Starting to use the internet at early ages seems to be a risk at later years in terms of internet addiction and cyberloafing (Kabasakal and Akada, 2018). It was also found that life goals significantly differ according to the time when participants started to use the internet. Similarly, the students who started to use the internet at middle school significantly differed from those who started to use the internet at high school. As class year increases, students set different life goals and develop different interests. Thus, life goals of the students who started to use the internet at early ages are expected to differ.

Finally, the study involved analyses focusing on the digital devices used in relation to cyberloafing levels. Cyberloafing levels did not differ according to whether the mostly used device is a desktop computer or smartphone; however, they differed according to whether the mostly used device is a laptop and tablet computer. The ratio of smartphone use in Türkiye is 77%, which is an important factor while interpreting the results of this study. The related studies found that widespread use of smartphones is related to increases in cyberloafing behaviors and mobile phone addiction (Gökçearslan et.al 2018). Life goals also significantly differed according to whether the mostly used device is a tablet computer or not. Another result of the study revealed that life goals of the participants did not significantly differ according to gender, age, class year and GPA. It might be assumed that the age range of the participants caused this situation.

The findings of the present study show a significant difference between cyberloafing profiles and life goals. In conclusion, it might be suggested that cyberloafing behaviors are quite widespread and might be examined in relation to various variables. Similarly, life goals have a multi-dimensional structure. Due to the limited number of studies dealing with cyberloafing and life goals, the results of the present study are remarkably noteworthy. It

will be useful to conduct more studies and duplicate the study with different age groups and by adopting different research models. Finally, both cyberloafing and life goals can be study topics for psychological guidance and counselling services

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